

ISic1527

I.Sicily inscription 1527

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Catacomb of S.Giovanni

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 26637

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Ἐνθάδε κίτε ὁ μα
2. καρίας μνήμης
3. Ἰωάννιος ὁ ἄμεν
4. πτος χρησιανὸς ζή
5. σας καλ(ῶς) ἔτη κβ
6. [---] τελευτᾷ πρὸ γ
7. καλ(άνδαις) Σεπτεμβρίω[ν]
8. ἐν ἰρήνη

Apparatus

Text after Agnello 1953 with slight changes based on Griesheimer 1989

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645027

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 39.1030

Agnello, S.L. 1953. Silloge di iscrizioni paleocristiane della Sicilia. Rome. At no.31
undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.

Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità*. At 22

Griesheimer, M. 1989. Quelques inscriptions chrétiennes de Sicile orientale. *Rivista di Archeologia Cristiana*. 65: 143-177. At 175 no.14

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic1527. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4354315>